

T.C.

ISTANBUL AYDIN UNIVERSITY

INSTITUTE OF GRADUATE STUDIES

How Influencers' Lifestyle can Affect Consumers' Eating Habits in Turkey

THESIS

Fardeen Amini

Department of Business Administration

Master's program

ORCID N:0000-0002-8894-4123

2022

Table of Contents

HOW INFLUENCERS' LIFESTYLE CAN AFFECT CONSUMERS' EATING HABITS IN TURKEY.	854
1. INTRODUCTION	857
1.2. Purpose of the study	857
The purpose of the study is to establish how influencers' lifestyle can affect consumers' eating habits in Turkey.	857
1.3. Research Objectives	857
1.4. Research Questions	858
2. METHODOLOGY	861
2.1. Research Design	861
2.2. Study Population	861
2.3. Sample Population	861
2.4. Sampling	861
2.5. Questionnaire	861
2.6. Data Analysis	861
2.7. Ethical Considerations	861
3.8. Limitations of the study	861
3. CONCLUSION	862

ABSTRACT

The primary aim of this study is to assess and examine the relationship between social media influencers' lifestyle and consumers eating habits. Quantitative research method is used in this study as it will provide statistical data and will help policy makers in managing public health by curbing the effect of influencers. For the purpose of this research, in line with the population of Data reported, there are 60 million social media users in Turkey so convenient sampling will be conducted for study. This research will use a sample size of 384 respondents determined by Cochran formula for large populations. Likert based questionnaire is given to the respondents and the data is assessed using AMOS software.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

These days, social media have an undeniable place in people's lives in almost all over the world (Hjetland, Schønning, Hella, Veseth, & Skogen, 2021). Influencer marketing is one of the famous ways that many brands and businesses use to introduce and advertise their products and services. It has been proved that social media influencers are able to affect our habits and behaviors by sharing their lifestyle and ads on different social media platforms. Though there are evidence that show social media and influencers can affect and alter behaviors related to diet and physical activity Goodyear et al (2021) some studies showed little or no effects.

Having a healthy diet is very important as (Yurtsever et al., 2020) and Turkey is not an exception. According to CDC report obesity can cause hypertension, high LDL cholesterol, low HDL cholesterol, type II diabetes, coronary heart diseases, stroke, gallbladder disease, osteoarthritis, sleep apnea and breathing problems, low quality of life, mental problems like depression and anxiety, body pain and difficulty with physical functioning (prevention, 2021). Childhood obesity can cause negative effects on children's different aspects of health including social, physical, emotional health and also their self-confidence (Sahoo et al., 2015)

According to Datareportal, there are 60 million social media users in Turkey. A study done on college students by Qingya Wang et al showed it is so probable that students are affected easily by social media because of attractiveness of social media. Based on this article social media even helped the college students to face their stress better and feel less pressure during academic semesters(Moshi, Tooher, & Merlin, 2020). Youth usually spend a lot of time on social media. A research conducted by Ghulam Shabir et al expressed that young people's attention for social media takes them away from their main studies.

Another survey conducted by Qin Moshi proves that participants on the survey, who were young people were greatly affected by social media influencers. Results showed that 90% of respondents did something because an influencer did a similar activity. Over half of the participants trusted products that influencers recommended and 80% were ready to try new things influencers offered. Participants were willing to trust influencers as they found social media a platform for more information and entertainment. Actually, the highly qualified content of the posts attracted their attention (Shan, Chen, & Lin, 2020).

The research will assess the different prevailing lifestyles, which is occurring amongst the people and how this affects the customer eating habits. This will guide on the marketing mechanisms that can be employed to induce the marketing of products amongst the customers. The study will establish the mechanisms that can be employed to identify the eating habits amongst the people in countries including Turkey. The study will inform the establishment of policy mechanisms necessary for inducing the management of eating habits to enable their satisfaction amongst the customers.

A. Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to establish how influencers' lifestyle can affect consumers' eating habits in Turkey.

B. Research Objectives

This research is going to find out:

Fig. 1

- If healthy lifestyle of influencer affects costumers' eating behaviors.
- If sedentary lifestyle of influencer affects costumers' eating behaviors.
- How much healthy lifestyle can affect costumers' eating behaviors.
- How much sedentary lifestyle can affect costumers' eating behaviors.
- If product placement has an effect on costumers' eating habits.
- If influencer's credibility has an effect on costumers' eating habits.

C. Research Questions

- Does healthy lifestyle of influencer impact costumers' eating behaviors?
- Does sedentary lifestyle of influencer impact costumers' eating behaviors?
- How much healthy lifestyle of influencer can cause changes in costumers' eating behaviors.
- How much sedentary lifestyle of influencer can cause changes in costumer eating behaviors?
- Does influencer's credibility have an effect on costumers' eating habits?
- Does product placement have an effect on costumers' eating habits?

D. Research Model

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Micheal Cross in his book explains Social media as a tool that helps individuals contact each other easier and it can help businesses get their messages to larger group of audience(Cross, 2013). Micheal Cross explains though social media is very useful in making interaction between people easier and it is a powerful method for companies and businesses to advertise their brand, social media is not riskless. Safety, job and business of a company are issues that can be affected by potential social media risks.

Social media is a tool which is web-based and gives the ability of communicating, sharing contents like pictures, videos and links of sources to its users (Gould, 2013).Social media can be defined as digital platforms that people and businesses can use them for content delivery and making engagement(Gould, Leland, Ho, & Patel, 2016). Weinberg defined social media as means that let people boost their services, products and websites via social media platforms and also social media gives users the chance to be heard by a larger group of audience that were not available in traditional media routs.

Digital marketing is a branch of marketing in which businesses and available or future costumers create and exchange value and products by using internet (Visser, Sikkenga, & Berry, 2019).

Digital marketing which is also known as e-marketing or internet marketing is very important to e-business, through digital marketing businesses can get closer to existing and potential customers, and also understand them and needs better. Digital marketing can cause additional value for company and products. Digital marketing has the ability of increasing distribution channels and promoting sales by managing marketing campaigns through online social media like affiliate marketing and search marketing. By using internet websites can be designed to make costumer leads, sales and after-dales services easier. Digital marketing gives the businesses the ability to put consumers at the middle of all online activities, for instance, receiving different user groups to examine website on various browsers in diverse settings on different connections.

The social media optimization which is known these days as social media marketing was explained in 2006 by Rohit Bhargava. Rohit Bhargava defined social media marketing as the ability of optimizing a website through content that contains links that importantly acts as means of trust and endorsement. Social media marketing is helpful in making brand awareness and also increases the views of products and services which were marketed before (Bhargava, 2012).

Social media is a method that gives people the ability of promoting their products, brands, services or websites by means of online social media routes in order to reach a bigger group of audience than traditional ways of advertising (Weinberg, 2009). Gordon Glenister believed basically, influencer marketing occurs when an influencer gets involved in efforts for promoting a brand, service or product(Hardy, 2021).Influencer marketing is a method that is used for promoting services, brands and products and is performed by chosen individuals who are able to effect buying behavior of target consumers.

Healthy diet is directly related to promoting a good health and healthy diet is directly the result of selections an individual makes for his or her eating habit. Healthy eating habit means consuming right amounts of essential nutrients from different food categories. The major aim of healthy eating diet is about taking balanced amounts of nutrients needed for body from vegetables, dairies, carbs, meat and other food categories. The main goal of any healthy diet is to keep a healthy intake and balance of food (Oraman, 2014).

Specialists have known food selection as a complicated behavior almost in all around the world because food choice can be effected by different factors (Koster, 2009). Realizing the reasons of using special kinds

of food in certain situations is very advantageous for promoting people's quality of life by suggesting dietary consultations in order to avoid health problems such as eating disorders and obesity. A healthy diet will result in healthy individual who will have less hospital expenses which is beneficial for society and government (Chambers, 2016)

As it was mentioned above, daily food selection can be effected by different issues such as biological factors (e.g. hormonal changes, hunger), sociological factors (e.g. culture and social situation), physiological factors (e.g. mood or stress), economical (e.g. e.g. being available and salaries), marketing factors (e.g. advertising and distribution), and costumer science factors(e.g. attitude and risk perception).

National and local studies showed though average Turkish diet provides enough energy and essential nutrients that are needed to be consumed daily, intake of riboflavin, vitamin A, animal protein and calcium was lower than specialists offer (nations, 2015).

Empirical studies established the relationship between the healthy lifestyles and consumption patterns (Andrews et al., 2017). The findings revealed that there is a positive significant connection between the variables. Andrews et al. (2017) contend that there is a positive connection between the healthy dietary lifestyles and consumption patterns for the fruits and vegetable. Coomarasamy, Wint, Neri, and Sukumaran (2014) the lifestyles for the people influence the patterns that reveal that are being provided in the healthy lifestyle constructs was demonstrated for positive significant for the consumption patterns.

Goetzke et al (2014) established that a significant connection between consumption patterns for the food and healthy lifestyles of the customers. Goetzke, Nitzko, and Spiller (2014) established that the cognition for the emotions provide a considered view of the determination of the health lifestyles through cognition in emotions not significant in the connection for the consumption patterns. Jayaraman, et al (2013) established that a health concern is taken as the determination of the health lifestyles for the not significant in consumption patterns for the people and commodities.

Sedentary behaviors and low activities levels are risk factors for the main chronic diseases such as obesity and type 2 diabetes, Cardionetabolic risk and mortality, the physical activities and fitness has been low, improve the health, and decrease the diseases, fragility, disables and mortality (Thorp, et al, 2019). The simultaneous sedentary behaviors involve the activities with low energies needed in expenditures for the metabolic equivalents performed for the main sitting activities spinning through associated to the consumption of unhealthy foods among the youths and the adults were connected to increase the occurrence of Obesity among the people in high probability forms for the management of chronic diseases.

Product Placement is a brand placement in program sponsoring, branding entertainment or product integrations in marketing, advertisement, promotions where the brand name, product, package, signage and other trade marks for the products is inserted into use. Product placement involves the audience attaining exposure for the brands in products during the natural processes. For the movies in television programs or content vehicles (Cebrzynski, 2016) the product placement for the popular forms of media in providing the exposure for the potentials in targeting the consumer and showing the brands needed in the consumption traits and settings for the products.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The study will use a correlation research design qualitative approaches in the course of the study. According to Creswell & Clark (2007), a correlation research design measures the relationship between two variables without the researcher controlling either of them. The design will allow for an estimation of the relationship between the study variables on influencers' lifestyle can affect consumers of eating habits in turkey and will use of correlation tests to assess the phenomenon under study. Quantitative approach will be used due to the fact that the quantitative method helps collect information which is coded, quantified and statistically analyzed generating statistical results. A quantitative descriptive research was conducted through a structured questionnaire. Questionnaire was provided in English and Turkish.

B. Study Population

The research considers the population of people in Turkey but especially those from Istanbul will be used to represent the entire population of the study. According to Datareportal, there are 60 million social media users in Turkey.

C. Sample Population

For the purpose of this research, in line with the population of Data reported, there are 60 million social media users in Turkey. As the population under study is big, the sample size was calculated by this formula: There are several methods of sample size determination based on the population. The study will use a sample size of 384 determined by Cochran (1977) formula for large populations.

D. Sampling

Convenient sampling will be conducted for study. The respondents who will be accessible first will provide the information for the study than those accessed later. Accessibility will be the basis of the selection of the respondents for the study.

E. Questionnaire

The study will employ structured closed ended questionnaires as the only source of data collection, closed ended questionnaires will be used in the data collection, will be distributed to the respondents involving the study to provide answers by ticking the best option that fit the response.

F. Data Analysis

The data collected will be coded, and sensitivity will be provide to assess the degree of the certainty on the information needed, will be checked for completeness and comprehensive. The data will be summarized, coded and tabulated, the descriptive statistics will be provided to analyze the bio-data of the respondents. Data will be analysed by using SPSS AMOS.

G. Ethical Considerations

To ensure that ethics will be practiced in this study as well as greatest confidentiality for the respondents and the data provided by them, important measures will be taken. All questionnaires coded to provide anonymity of respondents' responses.

H. Limitations of the study

Main limitation of this research is that the study focuses only on effects of influencers' lifestyle on their followers and other possible aspects of influencers' lives such as age and level of education are not considered. Convenient sampling would be held in the methodology.

CHAPTER 4

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to validate and assess the amount of influence on general public regarding eating habits due to social media influencers. Turkey uses social media and it's widespread, it offer the environment that are somehow favorable in influencing the marketing. There are many Turkish influences that specialize in the areas like fashion, sports, food, beauty and healthy lifestyles. This includes the content for the brands in the posts. The platforms influence the active forms such as Instagram and YouTube. The Instagram for Turkey forst was 20 most followed in the influences in listed forms for the 3 influencers posting in food and 2 influences for production of content connected to beauty or makeup's and lifestyles.

Turkey is located both in Europe and Asia and Mediterranean Sea is located in south of Turkey. So, eating habits in this country are influenced by three cultures including Mediterranean, Asian and European cultures (Sahingoz&Sanlier, 2011). Based on the Food and Agriculture organization of the United Nations, people from Turkey eat three main meals in day(nations, 2015). Their diet is mostly consisted of wheat products (like various kinds of bread), meat, legumes, rice and maize. In some areas of Turkey, fat is consumed as olive oil, in eastern parts sunflower oil and margarine are more likeable.

Among dairy products, Turkish people consume yogurt mostly. Vegetables and fruits have a significant place in their daily diet. Turkish people mostly use lamb and beef in their foods but consumption of these proteins has been decreased among people because of price raise in these products. In Turkish daily diet sweets, especially baklava and Turkish delight are inseparable(Batu &Kirmaci, 2009). Though traditional style of diet pattern is very popular in Turkey, people showed an increasing desire towards fast food in recent 30 years. Youth usually prefer fast foods with American style (like Mc. Donald, KFC, etc.). On the other hand elderly people prefer fast foods with Turkish style (e.g. doner, kebab) (Akbay, Tiryaki, & Gul, 2007). In Turkey, other factors like price, household features, and being healthy influence food choice. It is noted in the study that the majority of public get influenced easily and their eating habits are influenced by the influencers at social media. Social media plays an important role especially in the lifestyle of youth and young people easily get influenced by the eating habits of the influencers and tend to copy the lifestyle of their favorite influencers.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Aggarwal, A., Cook, A. J., Jiao, J., Seguin, R. A., Vernez Moudon, A., Hurvitz, P. M., & Drewnowski, A. (2014). Access to supermarkets and fruit and vegetable consumption. *American journal of public health*, 104(5), 917-923
- [2.] AL Kurdi, B. A. R. W. E. E. N. (2016). Healthy-food choice and purchasing behaviour analysis: An exploratory study of families in the UK (Doctoral dissertation, Durham University).
- [3.] Andrews, H., Hill, T. D., & Cockerham, W. C. (2017). Educational attainment and dietary lifestyles. *Food Systems and Health: Emerald Publishing Limited*, 101-20. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1057-629020170000018005>
- [4.] Bhargava, R. (2012). *Likeonomics: The unexpected truth behind earning trust, influencing behavior, and inspiring action*: John Wiley & Sons.
- [5.] Chambers, D. (2016). *Changing media, homes and households: Cultures, technologies and meanings*: Routledge.
- [6.] Cross, M. (2013). *Social media security: Leveraging social networking while mitigating risk*: Newnes.
- [7.] Gould, D. J., Leland, H. A., Ho, A. L., & Patel, K. M. (2016). Emerging trends in social media and plastic surgery. *Annals of translational medicine*, 4(23).
- [8.] Hardy, J. (2021). *Branded Content: The Fateful Merging of Media and Marketing*: Routledge.
- [9.] Hjetland, G. J., Schønning, V., Hella, R. T., Veseth, M., & Skogen, J. C. (2021). How do Norwegian adolescents experience the role of social media in relation to mental health and well-being: a qualitative study. *BMC psychology*, 9(1), 1-14.
- [10.] Moshi, M. R., Tooher, R., & Merlin, T. (2020). Development of a health technology assessment module for evaluating mobile medical applications. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 36(3), 252-261.
- [11.] Oraman, Y. (2014). An analytic study of organic food industry as part of healthy eating habit in Turkey: Market growth, challenges and prospects. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 150, 1030-1039.
- [12.] Sahoo, K., Sahoo, B., Choudhury, A. K., Sofi, N. Y., Kumar, R., & Bhadoria, A. S. (2015). Childhood obesity: causes and consequences. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*, 4(2), 187.
- [13.] Shan, Y., Chen, K.-J., & Lin, J.-S. (2020). When social media influencers endorse brands: The effects of self-influencer congruence, parasocial identification, and perceived endorser motive. *International Journal of Advertising*, 39(5), 590-610.
- [14.] Visser, M., Sikkenga, B., & Berry, M. (2019). *Digital Marketing Fundamentals: From Strategy to ROI*: Routledge.
- [15.] Yurtsever, S. G., Kaya, S., Arkalı, T., Müderris, T., Günaydın, P., & Küçükzeybek, Y. (2020). MEDİKAL ONKOLOJİ HASTALARINDA HEPATİT B SEROPREVELANSI. *PREVALENCE*, 30, 38.